

Examining the Innovative Leadership of School Principals from the Perspectives of Teachers

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ÖZET

This study aims to examine the perceptions of innovative leadership among school principals from the perspective of teachers. Conducted using quantitative methods and a descriptive design, the study's population comprised teachers serving in the Eskişehir Odunpazarı district during the 2022-2023 academic year. A sample of 334 teachers was included using convenient sampling method. Data collection instruments included the 28-item Innovative School Leadership Scale developed by Akyürek and Karabay (2022) and a researcher-developed personal information form. The conformity of the data to quantitative analysis methods was checked, revealing adherence to standard normal distribution and homogeneity of variances. According to the opinions of participating teachers, school principals' perceptions of innovative leadership are positive. Findings indicate that variables such as gender and subject area have statistically significant effects on perceptions, while other variables such as educational level, marital status, school type, age, and professional seniority do not affect perceptions. Overall, this research demonstrates that, from the perspective of teachers, school principals' perceptions of innovative leadership are generally positive. However, certain factors like gender and subject area may influence these perceptions.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Innovative leadership, Teacher Opinion, Leadership

INTRODUCTION

The rapidly evolving world in terms of technology and innovation constantly compels workplaces and corporate structures to adapt to the ongoing changes in order to sustain their existence. It is believed that corporate structures and work environments that struggle to keep up with these changes may cease to exist. It is essential for corporate structures and work environments to embrace innovations for the sake of productivity and sustainability (Slåtten & Mehmetoğlu, 2015).

It can be said that the primary concepts of adapting to and embracing innovations include change and change management. Initiating and implementing change within an organization hold significant importance in managerial processes, thereby facilitating substantial transformation. Organizations require transformation processes to gain a competitive advantage and ensure their survival within the competitive landscape (Selçuk, 2018). Managers, as they enhance their skills, can initiate, implement, and consequently position the organization differently from its competitors (Aydın, 2019). This scenario is applicable to educational organizations, like other organizational structures. Educational systems worldwide are influenced by the dynamically changing environment, resulting in various changes in school and educational systems over the last quarter-century (Şişman, 2021). In our country Turkey, the Ministry of National Education and its organizations have developed and attempted to implement educational programs and numerous practices. Changes in developed and developing countries affect changes in the education sector, which affect society as a whole (Özdemir, Aydın, & Bozkurt, 2013). While educational policies are determined by relevant decision-making bodies, implementing these policies in schools remains the most important duty of school administrators (Aktay & Çakır, 2018). School administrators can initiate change and foster an innovation culture in schools by prioritizing the measures determined by the Ministry of National Education.

In schools, administrators play a crucial role in managing and empowering change by taking the initiative (Aktay & Çakır, 2018). This is because school administrators are responsible for implementing change in schools and ensuring that change is accepted permanently within the school context, thereby

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maintaining educational activities. School administrators, who undertake such a significant role in schools, must lead the change.

Schools are incredibly important institutions for the implementation of the education system and the future of society. Therefore, schools need to adapt to changes and maintain a dynamic structure. Schools that adapt to change can sustain their existence and fulfill their responsibility of educating students to the best of their ability (Slåtten & Mehmetoğlu, 2015). Schools are organized to meet the needs of students and the expectations of society.

For schools to adapt to the change process in dynamic work environments, it is crucial for them to analyze change resources or forces effectively. These change resources come from both the internal and external environments of the organization. Organizations often focus on what and how to change during the change process, overlooking why they need to change. Therefore, understanding the source and reason for change is an essential starting point in change analysis and processes. For organizations to survive and succeed, they need to easily adapt to the demands coming from their internal and external environments. In summary, understanding the change resources coming from both internal and external environments is a critical step towards success in the change process. Organizational change, according to (Kılıçoğlu, Yılmaz, & Turan, 2014), is influenced by two factors: internal and external forces. Internal forces are factors within the organization that trigger change. These sources, sometimes not explicitly recognized, manifest themselves in forms such as low job satisfaction, inefficiency, or conflict (Kılıçoğlu, Yılmaz, & Turan, 2014). Human resources problems, arising from employees' perceptions of working conditions or the extent to which individual needs and desires align with organizational values, can cause change in organizations. In educational organizations, students' absenteeism, teacher turnover, the school's disconnection from its environment, and the negative impact of teachers' economic concerns on job satisfaction and motivation also indicate the need for change among school principals (Beycioğlu & Aslan, 2010).

Innovation is a concept derived from the Latin root "innovare," which means novelty. According to Aksel (2010) the concept of innovation does not exactly correspond to the term "yenilik" in Turkish. Although it is defined as novelty or renewal in Turkish, there isn't a direct equivalent to the word "innovation." Besides parallel meanings explained in different approaches and disciplines, innovation also implies doing something different or adapting to change. Conceptually, it is also used to refer to the preference for new methods in social, cultural, and managerial environments (Bulut & Arbak, 2012). Innovation is the most important tool for sustaining existence and thriving in a constantly evolving world. Organizations that do not struggle to adapt to this innovative situation with their employees and management can strengthen and continue their journey. Innovation acts as a compelling factor for organizations to adapt, thereby enhancing institutional success and competitiveness among other organizations (Akyürek, 2020). When examining researchers' definitions of innovation, the common point is the importance of adapting to novelty and implementing innovation. Despite having different structures at the institutional level, the concept of innovation in educational organizations represents a forward-looking positive change in organizational structures and educational activities due to advancing technology (Aydın, 2019).

Although the concept of innovation does not align precisely with the concept of novelty, it is generally understood as a process of renewal (Taş, 2017). However, not every innovation qualifies as an innovation; for it to be considered as such, it must provide economic or social benefits. Furthermore, perceiving innovation solely within the realm of technology would be misleading. Innovation occurs in various fields and takes different forms (Torun, 2016). In essence, innovation is a process in itself. Individuals who are able to follow developments, adapt themselves and their surroundings to these developments, take risks, manage these risks, and possess judgment skills play a leading role in innovation (Aydın, 2019). The cultivation of such individuals can only be achieved through innovation in education and educational practices.

It is important to know the ranking of countries in the Global Innovation Index (GII) when planning changes and transformations in education. This ranking plays a guiding role in identifying the weak points of countries in innovation practices, bringing out their strengths, and determining policies for positive development (Elçi, 2007). Overcoming this challenge and promoting innovative approaches in

educational environments are crucial for the education of our future guarantors, our students (Taş S. , 2007). This is because organizations and institutions that cannot adapt to innovation and change cannot sustain their existence, and nations that cannot keep up with this change and fail to educate their future generations accordingly cannot become effective and leading global entities.

As social beings, individuals seek to maintain their lives, establish social order, achieve their own goals, or manage the environments in which they find themselves, sometimes even desiring to be governed. In social life, rules, and the importance of living together and adhering to these rules during the implementation of these rules are crucial. Being a social being, individuals do not always seek to influence or govern those around them; oftentimes, they view choosing to be governed as a more reasonable option, avoiding responsibility. In line with these explanations, the concept of leadership has played an active role, been studied, and debated for years. The word "leadership" originates from the English word "leith" etymologically (Şentürk & Saġnak, 2012). Its meaning is defined as the influence, suppression, or attempt to suppress one group or individual by another group or individual in social life (Ünlü & Eroġlu, 2013). In general, based on the definitions made, a leader is described as a person who is followed in social life, and actions are taken according to the directives they give (Koçel T. , 2005). Leadership is the ability to influence people, and a leader is the person who demonstrates the ability to influence people and ensure their obedience and loyalty (Çetin, 2008).

Studies on the characteristics of leaders, how a leader should be, communication skills of leaders, and the effectiveness of leaders have been conducted in light of research on leadership theories and approaches. According to researchers, the notion that leadership is formed from innate characteristics inherent in individuals was widely accepted. Over time, the idea that behavioral characteristics are more important alongside personal qualities in leadership became a dominant understanding through studies. Research and time have revealed that the personal qualities and behaviors of leaders are insufficient in sustaining leadership situations and influencing people, leading to the emergence of studies in this field.

Leadership approaches are utilized to establish a theoretical framework for leadership and understand leadership practices. These approaches aim to explain what leadership is, what leaders do, and how leadership can be effectively carried out (Begeç, 1999). While research on leadership continues to be diverse, studies on the phenomenon of leadership are generally categorized into four main headings (Demir, Yılmaz, & Çevirgen, 2010).

Trait Approach: In the trait approach, it is believed that leaders' personality traits and social-physical characteristics are more prominent and dominant in influencing groups, and leadership is considered to be a talent that is innate rather than acquired (Akyüz, 2002). This approach seeks ways to select the right leaders, develop leaders' abilities, and identify the qualities required to succeed in leadership by analyzing leadership in terms of traits.

Behavioral Approach: This approach is produced in response to questions about the leader's tasks and how the leader's behaviors should be. In this approach, it is possible to acquire leadership behaviors through training, as the leader's behaviors play a crucial role in guiding the groups they influence and maintaining their loyalty (Begeç, 1999). Behavioral approach proponents have examined leaders in two dimensions: those who prioritize task-oriented leadership and those who prioritize social relationship-oriented leadership. In the leadership style that prioritizes social relationships, it is believed that the happiness of employees within the organization is important, and happy and peaceful individuals are more productive within the organization (Akyüz, 2002).

Managerial Leadership Approach: In the managerial leadership approach, interpersonal behaviors, informational behaviors, and decision-making behaviors in managerial tasks are discussed as three main types of behavior (Taslak, 2008). In this approach, many behaviors such as task allocation among individuals within the organization, motivation, communication and relationships between managers and employees, managerial decision mechanisms, and task allocations are distributed within the three main behaviors (Akyüz, 2002).

Situation Leadership Approach: This leadership approach focuses on the shaping of leader behaviors according to encountered situations. In the situational leadership approach, it is believed that leaders who adapt and develop their approach according to the current situation and encountered situations are more successful (Yurttaş, 2022). In this context, research has shown that the ability of leaders to develop

an approach based on the situation, not only relying on their personal characteristics but also in predicted and unpredictable events, is a key criterion for leadership success (Alkurt, 2020).

Research has clearly demonstrated a linear relationship between management style and leadership (Dayan, 2021). Guiding behavioral patterns play an effective role in motivating followers towards the goals set by the leader (Deniz, 2014).

Charismatic Leadership: Charisma is defined in the dictionary as the quality of creating great interest in one's personality, with an inexplicable charm and influence. In this context, charismatic leadership stands at the forefront of contemporary leadership styles (Alkurt, 2020). Individuals exhibiting charismatic leadership possess personal qualities and successful experiences, and they intervene at the right time with the right actions in situations they encounter (Demircioğlu, 2015).

Transformational Leadership: Transformational leadership is one of the modern leadership styles on which much research has been conducted. The essence of this leadership style is adaptation to change (Aydın, 2019). Leaders in this style do not hesitate to make risky decisions to adapt to change and to adapt their organization to it (Bağrıyanık, 2019). In transformational leadership, the leader is directly involved in the motivation of the employees within the organization. Because motivation is crucial in adapting to change (Çelik, 2003).

Autocratic Leadership: Autocratic leadership is a leadership style where all powers lie with the leader, and all decisions are made by the leader alone. In this leadership style, effective roles in determining the goals and plans of the organization or institution lie with the managers or leaders. Employees do not have a say in the formulation of these goals and plans (Altan & Özpehlivan, 2019). In a changing and evolving era, it is not considered a highly preferred leadership style.

Visionary Leadership: Visionary leadership is seen as the pioneer of strategic change and transformation in organizations. Their most prominent feature is their ability to view the process of change from different perspectives. In visionary leadership, the leader is the one who encourages the adoption of change within the organization and maintains the motivation of the employees in adaptation to transformation, with the ability to persuade them (Alkurt, 2020). Visionary leaders succeed in organizations with future dreams, while they may not be successful in organizations without a future vision or with weak ones.

Bureaucratic Leadership: Bureaucratic leadership style is preferred and seen in structures where the goals to be achieved by organizations and the activities planned to achieve these goals are distributed to employees within the organization under specific roles (Şakar, 2016). In this way, a structure is established where the goals to be achieved, the forms of activities, and who will perform these activities within the organization are clearly defined (Erdoğan, 1994). In bureaucratic leadership style, the authorities of managers within the organization and the tasks they will perform are clearly defined.

Innovative Leadership: There are many scientific studies on administrators and leadership concepts. Developments in information technologies, increasing levels of competition, diversity of services, and increasing expectations have increased the importance of leadership qualities that managers should have (Akyürek, 2020). Innovative management approaches applied by young and well-educated leaders in organizations are considered crucial for organizations to achieve their goals and future positions (Taşkiran, 2006). In light of this information, it can be said that leaders having an innovative approach are crucial for the future of their organizations.

The lack of shared vision between members of the organization and the adoption of a traditional controlling approach by management negatively affect organizational innovation processes. In traditional management approaches, contributions made by individual efforts and successes achieved do not help develop organizational culture because individualism prevails, and communication among members of these organizations is not healthy. The emergence of an innovative organizational culture is a matter related to leadership, internal communication, and the internalization of organizational goals and objectives (Uzkurt, 2008).

According to studies conducted in the field of innovation and leadership in the literature, the most important characteristics of an innovative leader can be listed as follows:

- ✓ An innovative leader should first and foremost be open to change, not resistant to innovation, and should try to implement these changes within the organization by following developments in the field (Akyüz, 2002).
- ✓ They should have analytical thinking skills and be able to analyze the risk factors of the organization well, and take necessary precautions for them (Dayan, 2021).
- ✓ They should follow innovative approaches and have a personal interest in this regard, researching current technology and management approaches (Gürbüz, Erdem, & Yıldırım, 2013).
- ✓ Innovative leaders should be bold in implementing new ideas and in this sense, they should be able to lead organization members by doing what is required of them (Şenel & Gençoğlu, 2003).

They should have a high level of awareness not only of the organization's risk factors but also of the opportunities available to the organization. They should be able to increase the motivation of organization members by evaluating opportunities well and improve the quality of products and services aimed at achieving the organization's goals and objectives (Dayan, 2021). An innovative leader should be able to develop a strategic plan for the organization and implement this plan (Akyürek, 2020).

Schools are among the most important stakeholders in the education system for producing students who meet the needs of the knowledge society. In this regard, the leadership roles of school principals become crucial in line with the goals set by policymakers (Gürbüz, Erdem, & Yıldırım, 2013). With the increasing competition in all fields, it can be said that the concept of innovation also affects educational institutions. According to Akyürek (2022), innovation as a concept is defined as activities that enable the discovery of new resources suitable for changing technology in organizational structures, and the utilization of these resources within the organization. It is believed that school principals have a significant responsibility in carrying out these activities, implementing them, and ensuring that teachers adapt to this change. Because the sustainability of organizations depends on their ability to reflect change and innovation in all aspects to their employees (Adıgüzel, 2012). School principals have significant responsibilities in reflecting change and innovation to all aspects of employees.

Organizations, which exist to meet the needs of individuals in line with their established goals, are among the institutions affected by change (Selçuk, 2018). As needs change, organizations must renew themselves, keep up with change, and develop appropriate products and services. Organizational managers are individuals responsible for determining the goals of the organization and ensuring that tasks and operations are carried out accordingly (Aydın, 2019). Organizational managers, who can either lead to failures or contribute to the success of organizations, must recognize, understand, and utilize changing needs and their impact on organizations in the most efficient manner in line with organizational objectives. Schools are open systems with human input and output. Every positive and negative change in the environment affects schools along with individuals in society. During this process, the physical environments of schools, tools and equipment used, implemented curriculum programs, school atmosphere, relationships between administrators, teachers, students, and the environment, and school culture are affected. New methods and techniques applied in the education system change the way communication and sharing occur among administrators, teachers, and students. School administrators' awareness of change and the needs of the era, their attitudes towards innovations, and their innovation competencies will affect both school success and the quality of education (Gürbüz, Erdem, & Yıldırım, 2013). In this context, it is believed that the findings obtained from research will contribute to identifying innovative leadership of school principals and serve as a resource for studies in this area.

METHOD

Model of the Research

The study, aimed at examining the innovative leadership of school principals from the perspective of teachers, was conducted using the quantitative research design of descriptive survey model. Descriptive survey method is a research model used to describe current situations and phenomena (Karasar, 2020). This method involves a broad data collection process to understand a phenomenon or situation from the past to the present. Researchers analyze existing sources (books, articles, reports, etc.) and use statistical techniques to explain the obtained data. The descriptive survey method is typically used at the beginning of research in a new field to synthesize existing information and establish a foundation. This method

helps researchers understand the basic characteristics, trends, and changes of the phenomenon while providing clues for further research or in-depth analysis (Karasar, 2020).

Universe Sample

The population of the study consisted of teachers working in public primary, middle, and high schools located in the Odunpazarı district of Eskişehir province during the 2022-2023 academic year. The population of the study comprised a total of 5200 participants. The sample size, which would be representative of the population, was calculated with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%, resulting in a sufficient sample size of 330 participants. The sample of the study consisted of 334 teachers determined through the convenience sampling method. The demographic information of the participating teachers is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Data of the Sample Participants

Participants		N	%
Gender	Female	176	52,7
	Male	158	47,3
Educational Background	Bachelor's Degree	241	72,2
	Master's Degree	93	27,8
Marital Status	Married	268	80,2
	Single	66	19,8
Type of School	Primary School	53	15,9
	Middle School	75	22,5
	High School	206	61,7
Age (Years)	22-25	7	2,10
	26-30	14	4,2
	31-35	53	15,9
	36-40	100	29,9
	41-45	85	25,4
	46 and above	75	22,5
Branch	Foreign Language	30	9,0
	Vocational	96	28,7
	Skills-Based	25	7,5
	Quantitative	68	20,4
	Verbal	97	29,0
	PCG	18	5,4
Professional Experience (Years)	1-5	15	4,5
	6-10	68	20,4
	11-15	65	19,5
	16-20	83	24,9
	21 and above	103	30,8
Total		334	100

Data Collection Tools

In this study, a questionnaire consisting of two sections was used. The first section included a personal information form where demographic information of participating teachers was collected. The second section comprised the Innovative School Leadership Scale, consisting of a single dimension and 28 items, prepared by Akyürek and Karabay (2022), and used with the necessary permissions. The internal consistency coefficient of the scale was reported as 0.989, indicating its reliability. The confirmatory factor analysis of the scale's unifactorial structure yielded a χ^2/df value of 7.41, which fell within an acceptable range of fit ($3 \leq \chi^2/df \leq 8$), indicating the validity of the scale's unidimensional structure.

The high average score obtained on the scale applied to the teachers participating in the research using a 5-point Likert scale indicates a high perceived level of innovative leadership. Since the participants' responses were collected using a 5-point equally spaced scale, the range of scores (Score Range = (Maximum Score - Minimum Score) / 5) was determined to be 0.80. The score intervals used in the evaluation of the scale are as follows: 1.00-1.80 very low, 1.81-2.60 low, 2.61-3.40 moderate, 3.41-4.20 high, 4.21-5.00 very high level.

Data Collection and Analysis

During the data collection phase of the study, the data collection tool was administered through both face-to-face surveys and web-based survey and data collection applications available on the internet to reach a larger number of participants. In this context, data collection was conducted during the spring semester of the 2022-2023 academic year. During this period, the survey form was made available to teachers working in public primary schools, middle schools, and high schools in the Odunpazarı district of Eskişehir province via the internet, and they were asked to fill it out. A total of 334 teachers participated in the "Perceptions of School Principals' Innovative Leadership" survey. Permission requests were submitted to the University Ethics Committees and the Ministry of National Education for data collection.

The responses collected from the participating teachers were transformed into a format suitable for quantitative analysis methods and necessary analyses were conducted using appropriate statistical methods in the SPSS software package. Upon examining the distribution of the dataset, it was observed that the skewness and kurtosis values met the assumption of a standard normal distribution. According to (Çolak, 2010), distribution is considered to be standard normal when the absolute values of skewness and kurtosis statistics are below 2. Frequency, mean, and standard deviation statistics were calculated for the data collected from the participants. To examine differences between groups, independent t-tests were used for independent variables consisting of two groups, and ANOVA analysis was used for independent variables consisting of three or more groups. The analysis results are presented in detailed tables.

FINDINGS

Findings on the Innovative Leadership Of School Principals from The Perspective of Teachers

Analyzes to determine the innovative leadership levels of school principals according to the teachers participating in the research are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Statistics on the innovative leadership of school principals from the perspective of teachers

Scale	N	\bar{x}	Skewness	Kurtosis	SD
Innovative Leadership of School Principals	334	3,46	-,567	-,150	,989

According to Table 2, the average innovative leadership level of school principals according to the teachers participating in the research was determined as $\bar{x} = 3.46$. It was observed that this determined level was high.

Gender-Based Change in Teacher Perceptions of School Principals' Innovative Leadership

The results of the t-Test, which was conducted to examine the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the gender of the teachers, according to the teachers participating in the research, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Gender-related changes in school principals' innovative leadership from the perspective of teachers

	Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	t Test	
					t	p
Innovative Leadership of School Principals	Woman	176	3,335	1,017	-2,514	,012
	Man	158	3,605	,938		
	Total	334				

According to the findings in Table 3, the innovative leadership of school principals varies depending on the gender of the teachers ($p < .05$). Male teachers participating in the research have higher perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership than female teachers.

Changes in Teacher Perceptions Regarding the Innovative Leadership of School Principals Depending on Educational Background

The results of the t-Test, which was conducted to examine the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the educational level of the teachers, according to the teachers participating in the research, are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Change in school principals' innovative leadership depending on their educational status, from the perspective of teachers

	Educational Background	N	\bar{x}	SD	t Test	
					t	p
Innovative Leadership of School Principals	Bachelor's Degree	241	3,427	1,020	-1,075	,283
	Master's Degree	93	3,557	,902		
	Total	334				

According to the findings given in Table 4, it was found that the innovative leadership of school principals did not show a significant difference depending on the education level variable of the teachers participating in the research ($p > .05$).

Change in Teacher Perceptions Regarding the Innovative Leadership of School Principals Depending on Marital Status

The results of the t-Test, which was conducted to examine the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the marital status of the teachers, according to the teachers participating in the research, are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Change in innovative leadership of school principals from the perspective of teachers depending on marital status

	Marital Status	N	\bar{x}	SD	t Test	
					t	p
Innovative Leadership of School Principals	Married	268	3,446	,994	-,649	,517
	Single	66	3,534	,970		
	Total	334				

According to the findings given in Table 5, it was found that the innovative leadership of school principals and teachers participating in the research did not differ significantly depending on the marital status variable ($p > .05$).

Changes in Teacher Perceptions Regarding the Innovative Leadership of School Principals Depending on School Type

According to the teachers participating in the research, the ANOVA results conducted to examine the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the type of school where teachers work are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: The change in innovative leadership of school principals from the perspective of teachers depending on the type of school

f, \bar{x} and SD Statistics					ANOVA Results						
	Branch	N	\bar{x}	SD	Sum of Squares		df	MS	F	p	Diff
I.L.S.P	(1) Primary S.	53	3,205	1,05	Between Groups	4,47	2	2,23	2,302	,102	-
	(2) Middle S.	75	3,463	,98	Within Groups	320,95	331	,97			
	(3) High S.	206	3,530	,97	Total	325,42					
	Total	334									

According to the findings in Table 6, the innovative leadership of school principals does not show a significant difference depending on the school types of the teachers participating in the research ($p > .05$).

Changes in Teacher Perceptions Regarding the Innovative Leadership of School Principals Depending on the Branch

According to the teachers participating in the research, the ANOVA results conducted to examine the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the teachers' branches are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: The change in innovative leadership of school principals depending on the branch, from the perspective of teachers.

f, \bar{x} and SD Statistics					ANOVA Results						
	Branch	N	\bar{x}	SD	Sum of Squares		df	MS	F	p	Diff
I.L.S.P	(1) Foreign Language	30	3,171	1,014	Between Groups	25,43	5	5,09	5,561	< ,001	2>6 3>6 4>6 5>6
	(2) Vocational	96	3,670	,872	Within Groups	299,99	328	,92			
	(3) Skills-Based	25	3,697	,894	Total	325,42					
	(4) Quantitative	68	3,533	,986							
	(5) Verbal	97	3,420	,982							
	(6) PCG	18	2,494	1,111							
	Total	334									

According to the findings in Table 7, the innovative leadership of school principals shows a significant difference depending on the branches of the teachers participating in the research ($p < .05$). Since the number of participants in the groups was not equal, a Bonferroni post-hoc test was performed.

Table 8: The change of innovative leadership of school principals between branch groups from the perspective of teachers

Branches		Mean Difference	SE	p - bonf
(1) Foreign Language	(2) Vocational	-,498	,200	0,200
	(3) Skills-Based	-,527	,259	,640
	(4) Quantitative	-,361	,210	1,000
	(5) Verbal	-,249	,200	1,000
	(6) PCG	,677	,285	,272
(2) Vocational	(3) Skills-Based	-,029	1,000	,215
	(4) Quantitative	,137	1,000	,152
	(5) Verbal	,249	1,000	,138
	(6) PCG	1,175	,000	,246
(3) Skills-Based	(4) Quantitative	,166	1,000	,224
	(5) Verbal	,278	1,000	,215
	(6) PCG	1,205	,001	,296
(4) Quantitative	(5) Verbal	,112	1,000	,151
	(6) PCG	1,038	,003	,245
(5) Verbal	(6) PCG	-,926	,003	,245

According to the results of the Bonferroni post-hoc test conducted to examine the differences between branch groups, the perception levels of teachers in the PDR branch regarding the innovative leadership of school principals are lower than the teachers in all branches except the Foreign Language branch ($p < .05$).

Age-related Changes in Teacher Perceptions Regarding the Innovative Leadership of School Principals

According to the teachers participating in the research, the ANOVA results conducted to examine the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the age of the teachers are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: From the perspective of teachers, the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the age of the teachers

f, \bar{x} and SD Statistics					ANOVA Results						
	Age (Years)	N	\bar{x}	SD	Sum of Squares		df	MS	F	p	Diff.
I.L.S.P.	20-25	7	4,253	,585	Between Groups	4,77	5	,954	,976	,432	-
	26-30	14	3,430	,994	Within Groups	320,65	328	,978			
	31-35	53	3,386	1,007	Total	325,42					
	36-40	100	3,447	,997							
	41-45	85	3,450	1,010							
	46 and above	75	3,486	,964							
	Toplam	334									

According to the findings given in Table 9, the innovative leadership of school principals does not show a significant difference depending on the ages of the teachers participating in the research ($p > .05$).

Change in Teacher Perceptions Regarding the Innovative Leadership of School Principals Depending on Professional Tenure

According to the teachers participating in the research, the results of the ANOVA conducted to examine the change in the innovative leadership of school principals depending on the professional seniority of the teachers are presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Change in innovative leadership of school principals depending on professional seniority from the perspective of teachers

f, \bar{x} and SD Statistics					ANOVA Results						
	Professional Experience (Years)	N	\bar{x}	SD	Sum of Squares		df	MS	F	p	Diff.
O. M. Y. L.	1-5	15	3,793	,639	Between Groups	3,159	4	,790	,806	,522	-
	6-10	68	3,378	1,097	Within Groups	322,259	329	,980			
	11-15	65	3,384	1,031	Total	325,418					
	16-20	83	3,442	,960							
	21 and above	103	3,539	,952							
	Total	334									

According to the findings in Table 10, the innovative leadership of school principals does not show a significant difference depending on the professional seniority of the teachers participating in the research ($p > .05$).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In our study investigating the innovative leadership of school principals from the perspective of teachers, it was observed that the innovative leadership of school principals was high according to the results of 334 participants. It can be said that this high level, as perceived by teachers, is important in terms of educational activities and the ability to adapt to change.

In the research, perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership from the perspective of teachers varied according to the participants' genders. Accordingly, it can be stated that male participants had higher perceptions of innovative leadership.

The study showed that the educational status of the participating teachers did not create a significant differentiation in their perceptions of the level of innovative leadership of school principals. It can be concluded that the educational status of teachers did not have an impact on the perception of school principals' innovative leadership.

The research found that the marital status of participating teachers did not create differentiation in the level of innovative leadership perceived by school principals. It can be stated that the marital status of teachers did not have an effect on the perception of school principals' innovative leadership.

The study revealed that the types of schools where participating teachers worked did not create differentiation in the perception of innovative leadership of school principals. It can be said that the type of school where teachers work does not have an impact on the perception of school principals' innovative leadership.

In the research, it was observed that the types of subjects taught by participating teachers led to differentiation in the perception of school principals' innovative leadership. In this context, according to the Bonferroni post-hoc test conducted to observe differentiation in detail, it was found that teachers in the PDR branch had lower perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership compared to all other branches except for the Foreign Language branch.

The study revealed that the ages of participating teachers did not create differentiation in the perception of school principals' innovative leadership. It can be said that the ages of teachers working in the institution did not have an impact on the perception of school principals' innovative leadership.

The research found that the years of professional experience of participating teachers did not create differentiation in the perception of school principals' innovative leadership. It can be concluded that the years of professional experience of teachers working in the institution did not have an effect on the perception of school principals' innovative leadership.

In our study investigating school principals' innovative leadership from the perspective of teachers, the Innovative School Leadership Scale developed by Akyürek and Karabay (2022) was used. This scale consists of 28 items and a single dimension. There are no negative items in the scale, and it was determined that the distributions of participants' responses to the scale items follow a standard normal distribution. The analysis resulted in finding that teachers' perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership were high. The average scores of responses to the scale items were generally in the moderate to high range. However, it was observed that the item with the highest average score was "The school principal ensures the sharing of newly learned information," while the item with the lowest average score was "The school principal makes an effort to master at least one foreign language in order to follow the innovations developing in the global context."

According to the findings of the study conducted by Rakhymzhanov and Kurt (2022), school principals' innovative leadership behaviors are at a high level. Similarly, the findings of the study conducted by (Pamuk, 2022) indicate that, according to teacher perceptions, school principals' innovative leadership is at a high level. It was concluded that the findings of the study are consistent with the findings of some studies in the literature while not fully consistent with others.

During the research process, it was observed that the perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership behaviors varied significantly according to the gender variable of the participating teachers. Pamuk (2022) found that there was a differentiation in favor of male teachers in terms of teacher perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership behaviors. On the contrary, according to the findings of the study conducted by Kazan and Özgenel (2021), there was no differentiation in school administrators' leadership and contribution behaviors towards development based on the genders of teachers. It is thought that this situation arises due to the disinformation created by the gender and professional seniority of teachers working in the province and district where the research was conducted.

According to the perceptions of teachers whose data were collected during the research process, it was observed that the educational level variable did not create a significant differentiation in the perception of school principals' innovative leadership behaviors. Akyürek and Karabay (2022) found that teacher perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership behaviors differed in favor of teachers with undergraduate education. Similarly, Kazan and Özgenel (2021) found that there was a significant differentiation based on the genders of teachers in the open leadership behaviors of school principals. The findings of this research were not consistent with these studies. It can be said that the expectations of teachers regarding innovative leadership behaviors increase with the increase in the level of education, and therefore, findings in this direction are obtained in the literature.

According to the perceptions of teachers whose data were collected during the research process, it was observed that there was no significant differentiation in school principals' innovative leadership behaviors according to the marital status variable of the participating teachers. According to the findings of the studies conducted by (Pamuk, 2022), no differentiation was found based on the marital status of teachers regarding school principals' innovative leadership behaviors. According to the findings of the study conducted by Bel (2022), the perception of innovative work behaviors does not differ depending on marital status. It was concluded that the findings of the study are similar to the research findings in the literature.

In the research examining school principals' innovative leadership from the perspective of teachers, the Innovative School Leadership Scale developed by Akyürek and Karabay (2022) was utilized. This scale consists of 28 items and a single dimension. There are no negative items in the scale, and it was found that the distributions of participants' responses to scale items follow a standard normal distribution. As a result of the analysis, it was concluded that teachers' perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership were high. The average scores of responses to scale items were generally in the medium to high range. However, it was observed that the item with the highest average score was "My school principal facilitates the sharing of newly acquired knowledge," while the item with the lowest average

score was "My school principal makes an effort to master at least one foreign language in order to follow innovations developed in the global context."

According to the findings of the study conducted by Rakhymzhanov and Kurt (2022) school principals' innovative leadership behaviors are at a high level. Similarly, the findings of the study conducted by Pamuk (2022) indicate that according to teacher perceptions, school principals' innovative leadership is at a high level. The results obtained from the study are consistent with the findings of some studies in the literature but not completely aligned with others. This discrepancy is thought to arise due to the disinformation created by the gender and professional seniority of teachers working in the province and district where the research was conducted.

According to the perceptions of the teachers whose data was collected during the research process, there was no significant differentiation in the innovative leadership behaviors of school principals based on the variable of school type of the participating teachers. A study conducted by Akyürek (2016) revealed that the type of school where teachers work does not lead to significant differentiation in the distributed leadership behaviors of school principals. Similarly, the findings of the research by Sabancı (2017) support these results, indicating that teachers' leadership perceptions do not significantly differ based on the type of school they work in. The findings obtained from the study are in parallel with research findings in the literature.

During the research process, it was observed that there was a significant differentiation in the perceptions of school principals' innovative leadership behaviors based on the subjects taught by the participating teachers. According to the findings of Bel (2022), there was no differentiation in the perception of innovative leadership behavior among employees based on the type of duty variable. However, the research conducted by Köybaşı, Beycioğlu, Uğurlu, and Özer (2017) revealed that the perception of school principals' leadership varies according to teacher branches.

When the responses of the teachers whose data was collected during the research process were analyzed, it was found that there was no differentiation in the views on school principals' innovative leadership behaviors based on the age variable. According to Pamuk (2022), there is significant differentiation in teachers' views on school principals' innovative leadership behaviors. Therefore, it can be inferred that younger teachers have higher expectations from school principals in terms of innovative approaches.

According to the views of the teachers whose data was collected during the research process, there was no significant differentiation in the perception of school principals' innovative leadership behaviors based on the professional seniority of the teachers. In the study conducted by Pamuk (2022), it was also found that there is no differentiation in the perception of innovative leadership behavior among teachers based on professional seniority. The findings of the research conducted by Bel (2022) also revealed that there is no differentiation in the perception of innovative leadership behavior among employees based on professional seniority.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings and results obtained in this research process, the following recommendations are provided for researchers and practitioners:

For Researchers:

- ✓ Conduct further studies examining the relationship between school principals' innovative leadership and variables such as teachers' openness to change, organizational commitment, and school climate.
- ✓ Expand the scope of research with larger and more representative samples to enhance the generalizability of findings on principals' innovative leadership competencies.
- ✓ Employ mixed methods research to delve deeper into the research topic and gain a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon.

✓ For Practitioners:

- ✓ Organize in-service training activities for educational administrators based on the findings indicating high perceptions of innovative leadership among teachers. This can help administrators stay updated on contemporary leadership approaches essential for organizational success.

- ✓ Consider integrating courses on Educational Leadership, similar to those offered in graduate programs, into undergraduate teacher education programs to equip future educators with leadership skills from the outset.
- ✓ Increase awareness of the importance of innovation in educational leadership at the provincial, district, or ministry levels by organizing awareness-raising events and workshops.

These recommendations aim to contribute to the enhancement of innovative leadership practices in educational settings and the professional development of educational leaders.

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